

FRIEDEL-CRAFTS' REACTION INVOLVING UNSATURATED KETONES AND ESTERS. PART VII. ALKYLATION OF *o*- AND *p*-CRESOL METHYL ETHERS WITH ETHYL ALLYLACETATE AND ALLYLACETONE

By O. P. VIG, S. S. SANDHU AND S. M. MUKHERJI

Aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction of ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone with *ortho*- and *para*-cresol methyl ethers has been studied, the condensation products serving as readily accessible intermediates in the synthesis of naphthalene derivatives. The reaction with allylacetone is accompanied *in situ* with cyclodehydration, rendering the approach to naphthalene derivatives still simpler.

In Part VI (this *Journal*, 1957, 35, 9) we reported the results of aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction of ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone with anisol. We also recorded therein the facile cyclodehydration undergone by the product from anisol and allylacetone giving rise to a still simpler route to naphthalene derivatives. The present communication describes the cationoid reaction of ethyl allylacetate and allylacetone with *ortho*- and *para*-cresol methyl ethers. Following the conditions described in the case of anisol (Part VI, *loc. cit.*) they gave with ethyl allylacetate, under the influence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, (I) and (VI) in 43 and 40% yields respectively. These esters were hydrolysed and cyclised through Johnson's inverse addition technique to the corresponding ketones (III) and (VIII), which were reduced and dehydrogenated to the respective naphthalene derivatives, (V) and (X), essentially according to the conditions laid down in the case of anisol (*loc. cit.*).

The orientation of the substituents in the products (I) and (VI) has been proved by independent and unambiguous synthesis of the corresponding acids, (II) and (VII), according to the following schemes :

Cresol methyl ethers (*o*- and *p*-) were then subjected to aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction with allylacetone at 0°-5°, exactly as in the case of anisol (*loc. cit.*). But in neither case could the expected ketonic products be isolated. Instead, we found that the initial Friedel-Crafts alkylation was accompanied *in situ* with cyclodehydration, because both the products, (XI) and (XIII), on dehydrogenation with sulphur smoothly furnished the corresponding naphthalene derivatives, (XII) and (XIV).

The enhanced tendency to cyclodehydration in these cases, in contrast to anisol (*loc. cit.*), can be explained on the basis of enhanced nucleophilicity of the aromatic

substrates. This is borne out by the increased yields, by about 10%, of the products of Friedel-Crafts' alkylation with ethyl allylacetate, when compared with that from anisol.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Ethyl γ -(3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-valerate (I).—Freshly distilled *o*-cresol methyl ether (75 c.c.) was allowed to react with ethyl allylacetate (20 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (40 g.), following the direction of Mukherji *et al.* (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 1499), and after working up the reaction mixture in the usual manner, 15 g. (43%) of ethyl γ -(3-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-valerate (I), b.p. 140-45°/7 mm., was obtained. (Found: C, 71.68; H, 8.90. $C_{15}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 71.97; H, 8.86%).

γ -(3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-valeric Acid (II).—The above ester (13 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with alcoholic caustic potash solution (KOH 8 g., water 5 c.c. and alcohol 165 c.c.) on the water-bath for 6 hours. The acid (II) was isolated in the usual way in 80% yield, boiling at 176-78°/6 mm. (Found: C, 69.86; H, 8.02. $C_{15}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 70.24; H, 8.10%).

The *S*-benzylisothiuronium salt of the acid (II) was prepared in the prescribed manner and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 119°. (Found: N, 7.49. $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 7.21%).

4:6-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-1-tetralone (III).—The acid (II: 10 g.) in dry benzene (25 c.c.) was converted into its acid chloride by PCl_5 (10 g.) in the usual way. The acid chloride without being isolated was cyclised by $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 7 g.), following the condition laid down by Mukherji *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) for the preparation of 4:6-dimethyl-1-tetralone, when 8 g. (80%) of the ketone (III) was obtained, b.p. 140-43°/8 mm. (Found: C, 76.30; H, 7.84. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 76.44; H, 7.90%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* of the above ketone was prepared by the sulphuric acid method and was crystallised as red flakes from ethyl acetate, m.p. 213°. (Found: N, 14.4. $C_{19}H_{20}O_5N_4$ requires N, 14.58%).

1:7-Dimethyl-6-methoxy-tetralin (IV).—The above ketone (7 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of amalgamated zinc (50 g.), toluene (50 c.c.), glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.), HCl (conc., 90 c.c.) and water (40 c.c.) for 32 hours in the oil-bath at 130-40°. Every six hours 5 c.c. of HCl (conc.) was added. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way when 6 g. (95%) of the tetralin derivative (IV) was obtained, b.p. 135-36°/5 mm. (Found: C, 82.32; H, 9.23. $C_{15}H_{18}O$ requires C, 82.10; H, 9.47%).

1:7-Dimethyl-6-methoxynaphthalene (V).—The above tetralin (3 g.) was heated with sulphur (1.25 g.) at 180-90° for 6 hours, and the reaction product was steam-distilled. The distillate after working up in the usual way gave 1.5 g. (50%) of the naphthalene derivative (V), b.p. 130-32°/2 mm. (Found: C, 83.64; H, 7.39. $C_{18}H_{14}O$ requires C, 83.83; H, 7.58%).

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from alcohol as red crystals, m.p. 144°. (Found: N, 9.90. $C_{19}H_{17}O_8N_3$ requires N, 10.12%

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

Ethyl γ -(2-Methoxy-5-methylphenyl)-valerate (VI).—Freshly distilled *p*-cresol methyl ether (100 g.) was subjected to the aluminium chloride-catalysed reaction with ethyl allylacetate (20 g.) under the same conditions of temperature and catalyst concentration as described in the case of (I), when 14 g. (40%) of the ester (VI) was obtained. b.p. 135-38°/6 mm. (Found: C, 71.75; H, 8.93. $C_{15}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 71.97; H, 8.86%).

γ -(2-Methoxy-5-methylphenyl)-valeric Acid (VII).—The above ester (14 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with alcoholic caustic potash solution (KOH 9 g., water 5 c.c. and alcohol 160 c.c.) for 14 hours on the steam-bath. After working up in the usual way, 9 g. (72%) of the acid, (VII), crystallised from petroleum ether (80°-100°), m.p. 94°, was obtained. (Found: C, 70.19; H, 8.24. $C_{13}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 70.24; H, 8.10%).

The *S*-benzylisothiuronium derivative was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 119-20°. (Found: N, 6.85. $C_{21}H_{28}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 7.21%).

4:8-Dimethyl-5-methoxy-1-tetralone (VIII).—The cyclisation of the acid (VII: 9 g.) was accomplished through its acid chloride which was obtained by treatment with PCl_5 (9.5 g.). When treated with aluminium chloride (6.5 g.) as in the case of (II), 5.3 g. (67%) of the ketone (VIII) was obtained, distilling at 150-53°/7 mm. (Found: C, 76.52; H, 7.83. $C_{13}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 76.44; H, 7.90%).

The *semicarbazone* of (VIII) was prepared in the usual manner and was crystallised as a colorless mass from dilute alcohol, m.p. 157°. (Found: N, 16.30. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 16.10%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared by sulphuric acid method and was crystallised from ethyl acetate as red needles, m.p. 224° (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.2. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.58%).

1:5-Dimethyl-8-methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (IX).—The above ketone (VIII: 5 g.) was refluxed for 36 hours with a mixture of amalgamated zinc (35 g.), toluene (30 c.c.), glacial acetic acid (1 c.c.), HCl (conc., 60 c.c.) and water (25 c.c.) in the oil-bath at 130-40°. After working up in the usual way 3.1 g. (67%) of the desired product (IX) was obtained as a colorless oil, b.p. 120-22°/3 mm. (Found: C, 82.00; H, 9.32. $C_{13}H_{18}O$ requires C, 82.10; H, 9.47%).

1:5-Dimethyl-8-methoxynaphthalene (X).—The above tetralin (IX: 2.5 g.) was heated with sulphur (1 g.) at 180-90° for 6 hours, when after the usual working up, 1.6 g. (64%) of pure (X) was obtained (distilled over sodium metal), b.p. 120-24°/2 mm. (Found: C, 83.57; H, 7.45. $C_{13}H_{14}O$ requires C, 83.83; H, 7.58%).

The *picrate* was prepared in the customary fashion and was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 161°. (Found: N, 10.40. $C_{19}H_{17}O_8N_3$ requires N, 10.12%).

1:4:7-Trimethyl-6-methoxy-1:2-dihydronaphthalene (XI).—*o*-Cresol methyl ether (75 g.) was treated with allylacetone (12.5 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (25 g.) under the same condition as in the case of (I) except that the temperature was never allowed to go beyond 5°, when 11 g. (40%) of (XI), b.p. 116-20°/4 mm., was obtained. (Found: C, 83.00; H, 8.73. $C_{14}H_{18}O$ requires C 83.16; H, 8.91%).

1:4:7-Trimethyl-6-methoxynaphthalene (XII).—The above product (XI: 5 g.) was heated with sulphur (1 g.) for 5 hours at 180-90°. On working up, the reaction mixture gave 3 g. (60%) of the naphthalene derivative (XII), m.p. 80° (crystallised from methyl alcohol). (Found: C, 83.6; H, 7.99. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 84.0; H, 8.0%).

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from alcohol as red plates, m.p. 139-40°. (Found: N, 9.36. $C_{20}H_{18}O_5N_3$ requires N, 9.79%).

1:4:5-Trimethyl-8-methoxy-1:2-dihydronaphthalene (XIII).—*p*-Cresol methyl ether (50 g.) was acted upon with allylacetone (10 g.) in the same way as described in the preparation of (I), the temperature being kept between 0° and 5°. After working up in the usual manner, 9 g. (41%) of the product (XIII) was obtained, b.p. 120-22°/5 mm. (Found: C, 83.23; H, 8.76. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 83.16; H, 8.91%).

1:4:5-Trimethyl-8-methoxynaphthalene (XIV).—The dihydronaphthalene (XIII: 5 g.) was heated with sulphur (1 g.) for 5 hours at 183-90°, when 3.3 g. (66%) of the above naphthalene (XIV) was obtained as a colorless liquid on distillation over sodium metal, b.p. 135-38°/6 mm. (Found: C, 84.12; H, 8.32. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 84.0; H, 8.0%).

The *picrate* was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from alcohol as red plates, m.p. 150°. (Found: N, 10.10. $C_{20}H_{18}O_5N_3$ requires N, 9.79%).

An Unambiguous Synthesis of the Acid (II).— β -(3-Methyl-4-methoxybenzoyl)-propionic acid (40 g.), prepared according to the direction of Desai and Wali (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **6A**, 144), was esterified by refluxing with a mixture of absolute alcohol (400 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 24 c.c.) on the water-bath for about 14 hours. After working up in the usual manner, 35 g. of the ester was obtained (crystallised from alcohol).

This ester (35 g.) was then treated in the cold with methylmagnesium iodide (prepared from 32 g. of MeI and 4.7 g. of Mg) in 125 c.c. of dry ether. After standing for an hour, the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath for about 3 hours and was then decomposed with iced HCl and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with 5% Na_2CO_3 solution and the alkaline washings were acidified with dilute HCl. The separated oil was taken up in ether and worked up in the usual manner when 28 g. of γ -methyl- γ -(3-methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-vinylacetic acid was obtained which without purification was refluxed with 225 g. of HI (*d* 1.7) and 23 g. of red phosphorus at 130-40° for about 16 hours. After working up in the usual way 10 g. of the reduced but demethylated acid was obtained which could not be distilled without charring. Therefore the crude product was directly methylated with dimethyl sulphate (15 g.) in presence of 10% NaOH (50 c.c.). The product obtained was separated and was then hydrolysed with 10% NaOH solution (50 c.c.) by heating on the water-bath for 4 hours. After extracting once with ether, the alkaline aqueous layer was acidified and worked up in the normal way, when the acid (II) (6 g.) distilled at 176-79°/7 mm.

The *S*-benzylisothiazuronium derivative of this acid (II) was prepared in the usual fashion and was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 118°. The m.p. remained

undepressed on admixture with the *S*-benzylisothiuronium salt of the acid (II), obtained through the Friedel-Crafts alkylation of *m*-cresol methyl ether with ethyl allylacetate.

An Unambiguous Synthesis of the Acid (VII).— β -(2-Methoxy-5-methylbenzoyl)-propionic acid (30 g.), prepared according to the direction of Desai and Wali (*loc. cit.*), was esterified by refluxing with a solution of alcohol (300 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 18 c.c.) for 12 hours on the water-bath. After working up in the usual way, 26 g. of the corresponding ester was obtained as a colorless oil, b.p. $172-74^\circ/5$ mm.

This ester (25 g.) was then treated in the cold with methylmagnesium iodide (prepared from 3.6 g. of Mg and 22 g. of methyl iodide) in ether (100 c.c.). The reaction mixture after standing for about 4 hours was refluxed for 2 hours on the water-bath and then decomposed with ammonium chloride solution. The ethereal layer was extracted with 5% Na_2CO_3 solution and the alkaline aqueous extract acidified with dilute HCl, when γ -methyl- γ -(2-methoxy-5-methylphenyl)-vinylacetic acid (20 g.) was obtained as a clear oil which without purification was reduced by refluxing for 15 hours with a mixture of red phosphorus (16 g.) and HI (*d* 1.7, 160 g.). The product was worked up in the usual way when the demethylated reduced acid (10 g.) was obtained which could not be distilled. This phenolic acid (10 g.) was directly methylated by treatment with dimethyl sulphate (15 g.) in alkaline solution (50 c.c. of 10% NaOH solution). The separated oil was then hydrolysed with 10% NaOH solution (50 c.c.) on the water-bath for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether and alkaline aqueous layer acidified with dilute HCl, when 4 g. of the acid (VII) was obtained. This was crystallised from petroleum ether ($80-100^\circ$), m.p. 94° . The melting point remained undepressed on admixture with the sample of (VII), obtained previously through the Friedel-Crafts' alkylation of *p*-cresol methyl ether with ethyl allylacetate.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
PANJAB UNIVERSITY,
HOSHIARPUR.

Received July 28, 1956.